

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most quite a few North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Will be dark or gentle brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not always black in color. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear can be found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 ft in size. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, however their fur can vary from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon events. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are some of the very best at climbing timber. Their relatively smaller dimension and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb bushes for protection, meals, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their diet is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Diet: Their varied weight loss program offers them the flexibility to live in a big range of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They are the almost certainly bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are essentially the most widespread of all bear species, found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are accountable for nearly all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per yr. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their spread-out nature and decreased habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a big construct, a dish-formed face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the tips, which led to the name of essentially the most well-known subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt younger mammals resembling elk and moose. Their shade varies from gentle blonde to dark brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet long, and have a shoulder peak of 3.3 feet. □□ Diet: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on [dog teddy bear big size](#) giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies are typically bigger than those discovered within the Rocky Mountains attributable to a richer weight-reduction plan. Each year there are 46 assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Known for their aggressive habits, grizzlies are answerable for essentially the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are nearly as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 feet lengthy, and four feet tall on the shoulder. □□ Diet: Their food plan is much like mainland grizzly bears. However, on account of more plentiful food sources, the islands can help a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to change into their own subspecies. This has led to a extra complex social structure which results in less battle between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears can be aggressive. On account of their isolation, there is only one assault on humans every other year. Largest species of bear in the world weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight-reduction plan is usually made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white however is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range within the snow-coated arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and will be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species because of lack of habitat from climate change. Despite their huge size polar bears will be quick, maintaining a 6 mph pace within the water. □□ Features: In comparison with other bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps received Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Weight loss program: Their diet consists mostly of animals, especially seals which they will odor from a mile away. Although they seem white, their fur is definitely clear and their skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears may be extraordinarily dangerous. They see humans as potential prey. Attacks are rare as a result of remote nature of their habitat. Known for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and sometimes common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account vulnerable. □□ Dimension: One of the smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand forty seven to 75 inches tall. □□ Food plan: Relying on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on people are

increasing as individuals encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They're one in every of the simplest bears to tame (and subsequently frequent in circuses), but Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its food plan is bamboo. In reality, the second person in historical past to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while protecting his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body. □□ Location: Pandas are found solely in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they're thought of a vulnerable species. □□ Measurement: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and might be over four feet tall, a powerful feat contemplating they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It additionally has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in gentle brown and white. □□ Weight loss plan: Not like different bears the panda's weight loss plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Options: The large panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them regular: they poop over 40 instances a day! □□ Dangerous? Assaults are rare however harmful, given that pandas have one in every of the highest chew forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is discovered in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is unsure however thought-about susceptible and on the decline resulting from loss of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and other body elements utilized in conventional medicines. □□ Size: They stand solely 39 to 55 inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a short snout. They are named for his or her pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that appears like a rising sun. They also eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Weight loss program: Sun bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In actual fact, they have an extremely lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? Resulting from its shy nature, assaults are uncommon. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the title sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of lower than 20,000, they're thought of weak. □□ Dimension: They're fifty five to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Features: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they are simple to inform apart from other Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very fast and may out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the wrong way up from timber. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their massive curved claws. □□ Eating regimen: Their food plan consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Dangerous? They're probably the most aggressive bears, with the most attacks on people, largely due to shock encounters. They blow the dust round with massive puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not combine effectively with rhinos and elephants, often charging at each other when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's last brief-faced bear. The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that seem like glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Dimension: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to 79 inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's final quick-confronted bear and the only bear native to South America. □□ Features: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that typically appear like glasses. They spend most of their time in timber where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard precious fruit and carcasses. □□ Eating regimen: Spectacled bears are largely herbivores with a weight loss program consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they'll opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Dangerous? Living in distant mountains, these shy bears could be the least harmful of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears however bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is nearer to the polar bear. They characteristic the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, however have not been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA assessments have been unable to determine what sort of bear it was. Adorable koalas aren't bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they're indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in space. Most bear assaults occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Red pandas? They're in their own household which might be closer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS. Watch for bear scat and bear tracks

which will indicate a bear is close by, wherein case you want to be additional vigilant. Here are a couple of ideas you should use to prevent bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe. 2. MAKE NOISE. This helps bears know you're here so they do not by chance startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. KEEP YOUR DISTANCE. Whereas you will have nice intentions, a bear is prone to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. Secure YOUR SCENTED Objects (AT CAMP). When you see a bear, do not try to strategy or feed it. This includes meals, but additionally your toiletries, for instance. Whichever methodology you select, ensure that it is no less than 200 toes away from your tent so you don't appeal to bears to your campsite. 4. Stay CALM. If you happen to meet a bear, do not run. Attempt to make your self look as big as attainable, waving your arms above your head. You may as well extend a jacket above your head to make yourself look larger. Lock these items in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Do not scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT). Communicate to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 feet) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward. 6. Fight Again. If all else fails and a bear assaults you, don't play useless. Which bear is the largest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 ft long, and 4.0 to 5.25 ft tall, the biggest bear by both size and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight again with all your strength and hope that it'll back down. Which bear is probably the most dangerous? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is known for the most attacks. When in bear country, it's at all times clever to hold bear spray. It's well deserved, especially when cubs are around. Each year there are approximately 46 grizzly assaults, 6 resulting in loss of life. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome repute. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most prone to see an American black bear, on common there is only one attack per 12 months. By way of raw bite energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chunk reigns supreme. All bears are sturdy and to not be messed with. When utilizing the bite power quotient (chunk power relative to size), the sun bear packs probably the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fire but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he turned an icon and to at the present time is the star of the longest-working public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. More importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous thru-hikers to try to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo is a sloth bear, although he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a responsibility-free lifestyle. He additionally may be the primary bear to obtain his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son often would go to on the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada near where he was from. Chris also wrote The right way to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal elements backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to offer quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic ideas, guides and how-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

